

PARENTAL PERCEPTIONS ON FACTORS INFLUENCING THE DECLINE IN PARTICIPATION FOR SCIENCE, TECHNOLOGY AND ENGINEERING ADMISSION SELECTION

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ABSTRACT

The educational landscape is undergoing a significant transformation. The study sought to determine the parental perception of the factors influencing the decline in participation in Science, Technology, and Engineering programs that concern household income and educational attainment. A quantitative questionnaire survey checklist was distributed to gather responses through an online platform. The responses were analyzed using frequency, standard deviation, and ANOVA. The study revealed that parental household income is less likely to affect their participation in the program which is reflected in significant values of 0.195, 0.511, and 0.947 respectively, which is all higher than the alpha value of 0.05. Likewise, the result revealed between the factors and parental education attainment with $p = 0.441 > 0.05$, $p=0.707>0.05$, and $p=0.678>0.05$ alpha value. These results presented that the family income and educational attainment of the respondents have not influenced the decline in participation of the students in the Science, Technology, and Engineering program admission selection.

Keywords: *STE program, decline, parental perception, admission*

INTRODUCTION

The educational landscape is undergoing a significant transformation. In the recent years, the integration of Science, Technology, and Engineering (STE) program have gained the prominence and trust in educational environment or institution nationwide

which is essential in critical thinking, problem-solving abilities, scientific literacy, and life application. In our 1987 Constitution, Article XIV, sec. 10 stated that “Science and technology are essential for national development and progress. The State shall give priority to research and development, invention, innovation, and their utilization; and to science and technology education, training, and services”. This become the basis of Department of Education Order, no.55, s. 2010, its goal is to strengthening science and mathematics education at the secondary level. The integration of Science, Technology, and Engineering (STE) programs has become more well-known and trusted in educational settings across the country in recent years and students’ career choice intention was influenced by this program (Tey, Moses, Cheah, 2020).

Gülhan (2023) revealed that parental involvement in their children's education can have a significant impact on their success and it plays a significant role in forming students' minds and experiences (Tran et al., 2020). According to Duxbury, et.al (2021), parents engaging in their child school events and supporting their children’s interest in STEM (Ballavaram,2023) matters on their child's education while also learning more about their child's academic progress and potential obstacles. The trust and harmonious relation of the parents and the school, create a good influence, source of motivate and success of their child.

The number of interested students from Pililla and neighboring towns' elementary schools who would like to be considered for the incoming grade 7 Science, Technology, and Engineering program has declined over the last three years. The school faces challenges in selecting qualified students to fill the 80 available slots for incoming Grade 7 in the said program. However, there are difficulties in motivating parents and students from the top classes to actively participate in the admission selection process.

This aim to analyze the factors influencing the decline in participation for Grade 7 STE admission selection as perceived by the parents. This proactive approach not only safeguards the integrity of the STE program but also fosters a culture of continuous improvement and innovation that help the students reach their full potential and success in science-driven world.

Research Questions

Given the foregoing discussion, the researcher undertakes on the study with the questions “What are the factors influencing the decline in participation in STE 7 admission selection as perceived by the parents?”, specifically, the study will aim to answer the following questions: 1. What is the profile of the respondents in terms of 1.1 household income and 1.2 Educational attainment? 2. What are the perceptions of the parents on the factors influencing the decline in participation in grade 7 Science, Technology and Engineering program admission selection with respect to the following factors: 2.1 academic performances, 2.2 awareness and information and 2.3 program reputation. 3. Is there a significant difference in the respondents’ perception on the factors that contribute to the declining participation in grade 7 STE program concerning the different aforementioned variables and the respondent’s profile? Thus, proving the null hypothesis that there is no significant difference in parental perceptions on the factors influencing the decline in participation in Science, Technology and Engineering 7 admission selection when considering the respondents’ profile and the specified factors.

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

The study was utilized a descriptive research design, focusing on collecting detailed quantitative data to achieve a comprehensive understanding of the parents' perceptions regarding the Science, Technology, and Engineering (STE) program. To achieve this, a structured questionnaire consisting of 30 closed-ended questions will be administered to the parents. These questions are carefully designed and validated to elicit information. By utilizing a quantitative approach, this research aims to systematically analyze and interpret the data to identify potential areas of improvement within the STE program.

Study Site and Respondents

The research will be conducted in two schools within town proper that has pilot sections and are primary feeder schools for Pililla National High School, District of Pililla in the Division of Rizal, Region IV -A, Philippines. This is one of the schools in Rizal Province that offering Science, Technology and Engineering (STE) program.

The study included 65 respondents out of 80 parents who were asked to participate in the study. These parents contributed their responses through either an online platform or by completing a printed questionnaire checklist. This ensured an accessible method for data gathering and allowing the participants to do it in their most convenient time. This aimed to maximize their participation rates and gather comprehensive insight from the respondents.

Research Instrumentation

The researcher will use a questionnaire survey to determine the parental perspective about the Science, Technology, and Engineering programs, with closed-ended questions and a Likert scale rating. The delivery of survey questionnaires will be administered online or personally. The demographic data of the respondents will also be collected to find out if it influences the decrease in participant rate.

The researcher seek help from experts to validate questionnaire to ensure it clarity, and conciseness. After the validation, the researcher asked permission to the Public School district Supervisor in the District office and the school principal of the school under the study before it was conducted. After the approval granted, the researcher informed the parents of incoming grade 7 students through their class adviser. To ensure that the parents had a clear understanding about the study, they were given ample time to respond and at their own convenience. The questionnaire was presented in both English and Filipino languages to ensure to accommodate broad spectrum of respondents. Parents were assured that their responses would be kept confidential and used solely for research purposes.

Furthermore, the result of this study would serve as the basis of development or enhancement for the betterment of the STE program that would benefit educators, students and educational community.

Data Analysis

For the study titled "Parents' perception on the factors influencing the decline of participation for STE Admission Selection," data analysis will involve rigorous quantitative methods. For question 1, frequency, percentage and rank distribution were utilized to analyze data while in question 2, mean and standard deviation were employed to determine the factors influencing the decline in participants rates. To ascertain whether the hypothesis is accepted or rejected One-way Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) was used. This comprehensive approach will provide a detailed understanding of the factors contributing to the decline in participation for STE admission selection. The proponent analyzed the data using SPSS software and provided a concise narrative interpretation.

RESULTS

Profile of the respondents

Table 1. Household income of the respondents

Household income	Frequency	Percentage	Rank
Below ₱ 15,000	18	27.7	2
₱15, 001 - ₱30, 000	34	52.3	1
₱30,001 - ₱60,000	8	12.3	3
₱60, 001 – 150, 000	4	6.2	4
Above ₱150,000	1	1.5	5
Total	65	100.00	

The profile of the respondents showed that there were 27.7% have household income of below ₱15, 000, 52.3% of them earned ₱15, 001 - ₱30, 000, 12.3% were earned ₱30,001 - ₱60, 000, 6.2% received an income of ₱60, 001 - ₱150, 000 and 1.5% earned above ₱150, 001 and above, respectively.

Table 2. Educational Attainment of the respondents

Educational level	Frequency	Percentage	Rank
Elementary	1	1.5	5
High School	17	26.2	2
Vocational	5	7.7	3
College degree	38	58.5	1
Post-graduate degree	4	6.2	4
Total	65	100.00	

The data of the respondent's educational attainment displays a diverse range of background. A majority of 38 (58.5%) were college graduates. Following this, 17 respondents (26.2%) have completed high school. Vocational certificates or short courses have been attained by 5 respondents (7.7%). Additionally, 4 respondents (6.2%) are pursuing post-graduate degrees while 1 respondent (1.5%) has graduated from elementary level. This data highlights the predominance of higher education among the surveyed group.

The parental perceptions on factors influencing decline in participation Science, Technology and Engineering program admission selection.

Table 3. Parental perceptions on factors influencing decline in participation in terms of Academic Performance

Statement	Mean	Standard deviation(\pm sd)	Adjectival Rating
1. My child's performance in science influenced our decision regarding the STE program	4.46	0.772	Strongly Agree
2. My child's performance in Math influenced our decision regarding the STE program	4.40	0.880	Strongly Agree
3. I believe my child needs strong grades in Science and Math to succeed in the STE program.	4.43	0.728	Strongly Agree
4. My child's overall academic performance was a major factor in our decision about STE program.	4.40	0.862	Strongly Agree
5. I consider my child's interest in science when deciding on the STE program	4.43	0.809	Strongly Agree
6. I consider my child's interest in Math when deciding on the STE program	4.40	0.880	Strongly Agree
7. I believe that the STE program offers significant benefits for my child.	4.77	0.523	Strongly Agree
8. I believe my child is academically ready for the challenges of the STE program.	4.52	0.589	Strongly Agree
9. Enrolling my child in the STE program would encourage them to improve their academic performances in science and math.	4.82	0.464	Strongly Agree
10. My child's current academic performance in science and math is a	3.43	0.984	Agree

good indicator of their potential success in STE fields.			
Overall	4.41	0.749	

The table presented that statements from 1 to 9 had an adjectival rating of “Strong Agree” indicating that the academic performances of the respondent’s children was the key factor in their participation in the STE program. Notably, statement 9 presented the highest weighted mean of 4.82 (± 0.464), while the lowest was 3.43 (± 0.984) of statement 10.

Table 4. Parental perceptions on factors influencing decline in participation in terms of Awareness and Information

Statement	Mean	Standard deviation(\pmsd)	Adjectival Rating
1. I am well-informed about the STE program offered at our school.	4.69	0.498	Strongly Agree
2. I am aware of STE grade 7 admission program.	4.75	0.434	Strongly Agree
3. My child’s school provide sufficient information about the STE program.	4.54	0.561	Strongly Agree
4. The information about STE program provided by the school is easy to understand.	4.52	0.640	Strongly Agree
5. The school conducts effective campaign program for the STE admission.	4.55	0.638	Strongly Agree
6. The STE admission process is straightforward.	4.57	0.558	Strongly Agree
7. I find the STE grade 7 admission accessible (school fb page, flyers and brochure).	4.49	0.590	Strongly Agree
8. The school effectively communicates updates and detailed about the STE program.	4.52	0.615	Strongly Agree
9. The school provides adequate opportunities for parents to ask questions and receive answer about the STE program.	4.46	0.792	Strongly Agree
10. The information provided by the school has positively influenced my decision to consider enrolling my child in the STE program.	4.49	0.687	Strongly Agree

Overall	4.56	0.601	
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The table reveals that all the statements received a rating of “Strongly Agree”. Among these, statement 2 achieved the highest weighted mean of 4.75 (± 0.434), indicating the strong consensus among respondents. Conversely, statement 9 had the lowest weighted mean of 4.46 (± 0.792), though it still reflects a high level of agreement. Overall, the data suggests that respondents well well-informed about the admission process and selection criteria, as evidenced by their agreement across statements.

Table 5. Parental perceptions on factors influencing decline in participation in terms of Program Reputation

Statement	Mean	Standard deviation(\pmsd)	Adjectival Rating
1. I am aware of the success and achievement of students who have completed the STE program.	4.72	0.516	Strongly Agree
2. The STE programs offer valuable extracurricular and enrichment opportunities that enhance the educational experiences.	4.63	0.547	Strongly Agree
3. The STE program is known for being inclusive and welcoming to all students.	4.68	0.533	Strongly Agree
4. The STE program is well-regarded for preparing students for success in higher education.	4.68	0.533	Strongly Agree
5. The school administration strongly supports and invests in the STE programs.	4.66	0.477	Strongly Agree
6. Teachers involved in the STE program are well-regarded and respected for their expertise.	4.54	0.588	Strongly Agree
7. I believe that participation in the STE program aligns well with future educational and career opportunities for students.	4.82	0.391	Strongly Agree
8. I believe that the STE program positively impacts on students’ overall development.	4.78	0.414	Strongly Agree
9. The school actively collaborates with parents to ensure the success and well-being of students in STE program.	4.63	0.486	Strongly Agree

10. I believe that the teachers in STE program are highly qualified and possess the necessary credentials.	4.60	0.581	Strongly Agree
Overall	4.67	0.507	

In table 5 showed the respondents replied in all the statements with a remark “Strongly Agree”, with the highest weighted mean of 4.82 (± 0.391) of statement 7 and lowest weighted mean of 4.54 (± 0.588). It interpreted that the respondents were strongly agree on the program implementation.

Significant Difference of parental perceptions on Academic performance as factors influencing decline in participation and profile.

Table 6. Mean comparison between parental perceptions of factors influencing decline in participation (grouping variable: household income)

Factors	Mean	Standard deviation	f-value	Significant value	Interpretation	Decision
Academic Performance	45.31	5.626	1.565	0.195	Not Significant	Accepted
Awareness and Information	45.40	4.812	0.834	0.511	Not Significant	Accepted
Program Reputation	46.68	3.941	0.182	0.947	Not significant	Accepted

$\alpha = 0.05$ level of significance

The table shows that there is no significant differences between these factors and variables as reflected in significant value of 0.195, 0.511 and 0.947 respectively, which is all higher than the alpha value of 0.05. Therefore, the null hypothesis is accepted. This is supported in the findings of Betancur, et.al (2018) that there are only moderate gaps related to family income. Instead, it is mathematics and reading achievement influence in science achievement. According to Machebe, Ezegbe, & Onuoha (2017), parent’s financial status less likely to affect the academic performance of students but the parental support and involvement matter most.

Table 7. Mean comparison between parental perceptions of factors influencing decline in participation (grouping variable: Educational Attainment)

Factors	Mean	Standard deviation	f-value	Significant value	Interpretation	Decision
Academic Performance	45.31	5.626	0.951	0.441	Not Significant	Accepted

Awareness and Information	45.40	4.812	0.540	0.707	Not Significant	Accepted
Program Reputation	46.68	3.941	0.580	0.678	Not significant	Accepted

$\alpha = 0.05$ level of significance

The table shows that there is no significant differences between academic performance, awareness and information and program reputation as gleaned from the table. The $p = 0.441 > 0.05$, $p=0.707>0.05$ and $p=0.678>0.05$ alpha value respectively. Hence, the null hypothesis was all accepted. According to Betancur (2018), parental education has smaller and indirect effect to the study of their child in particular in the access in science learning. This is also supported in the study of Siregar, Rosli & Nite (2023) that parental educational attainment does not always contribute to the students' interest in STE program. Similarly, in the study of Idris, Hussain &Ahmad (2020) that parents' educational attainment has no significant correlation with son/daughter academic performance.

DISCUSSION

As revealed in the study, both household income and parental educational attainment were not major hindrances in the participation in the selection process in STE. Other factors that make the parent and the students hesitant to participate in the selection activity appear in the selection activity. The leaders and coordinators must think of a scheme to boost the interest of the students from elementary to achieve the criteria as requirement in the selection.

By proactively addressing these factors and fostering a supportive environment that encourages both students and parents to actively participate, educational institutions can effectively cultivate a more inclusive and diverse pool of participants in STE programs. This approach not only promotes equity and accessibility but also harnesses untapped potential among young learners, paving the way for a more robust future workforce in science, technology, and engineering.

Conclusions

Learning and interest of the students in the Science, Technology, and Engineering program vary among individual and are influenced by family support. The study's analysis revealed that the parental household income did not pose a barrier to participation in the STE program.

Furthermore, the study concluded that the respondents' educational attainment did not impact the participation rate in the STE admission selection. This indicates that parents' education levels were not concern in the decline of participation rate.

Recommendations

Recommendations were given on the basis of the above findings:

1. The study could be expanded to include more contexts and variables, involving a larger sample of STE community to provide a broader understanding of the factors influencing participation.
2. Conduct another study to further explore the challenges and conflicts experienced by the STE learners may help identify potential causes for the decline in participation rate.
3. Utilizing mixed-method research design could harvest more comprehensive responses and data, offering deeper insights into factors affecting STE program participation.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The author declares that strict adherence to the ethics of research was maintained, no conflict of interest exists in the conduct of the study, plagiarism was strictly avoided and there was no bias in the interpretation of the findings.

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